

PreMETS

**Predictive Maintenance Education & Training System:
An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in
Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial
cooperation, education, and training**

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D6.1 Macro Quality Assurance Plan

Final

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Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
AB	Advisory Board
DG	Dissemination Group
EC	European Commission
MC	Management Committee
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Officer
QCP	Quality Control Panel
QM	Quality Manager
StC	Steering Committee
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Terminology	
Conformity	The fulfilment of a specified requirement by a quality characteristic of an item or service, the assessment of which does not depend essentially on time.
Quality system	The organizational structure, responsibilities, activities, resources and events that together provide organized procedures and methods of implementation to ensure the capability of the Partner / Consortium to meet quality requirements.
Quality	The totality of features and characteristics of a prototype or service that bear on its ability to satisfy a given need.

Section 1. Quality assurance plan (T6.1)

Introduction

This document has been prepared for internal use for an efficient output development and open innovation and co-creation framework by Helixconnect Europe S.R.L and the other PreMETS project partners. It shall T the project partners with the necessary details and tools to effectively undertake the internal and external quality management of the project throughout its duration, in particular this refers to the scope and objectives, methodology and tools for quality assurance of this project. Formative evaluation results will be used. It shall facilitate the recording of the results in each phase of the project.

The main aims and objectives of this document are:

- To identify and measure the project's performance (outputs) and progress of process
- To raise awareness about quality within the project and support decision making processes,
- To provide feedback, particularly improvement potentials related to processes and outputs to coordinator and project partners about these,
- To contribute to clear user orientation in the development of project outputs.

A. Aim and objectives of the project - overview

Predictive Maintenance (PM) is a critical element for the optimization of sources used in the economy and on fundamental infrastructure systems. The critical role of PM (as an emerging work field) and the blooming prospects of its market, deems crucial the need to develop comprehensive training systems specialised on Predictive Maintenance to properly prepare the next generation of human capital that can effectively apply PMS across a wide variety of industrial/manufacturing infrastructure and equipment. The need for effective and widely used, education, training, testing, and certifying methodologies, is a key component in assuring the societal, environmental, and economic benefits that Predictive Maintenance can offer to the industrial sectors in Europe.

The aim of the PreMETS project is to introduce an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training for the development of a coherent digital platform that covers all aspects of the PM training process. In this context, the general objectives of PreMETS (linked to the goals of the call) are:

- Fostering new, innovative and multidisciplinary approaches to teaching and learning in the field of PM by introducing an innovatively co-created PM curriculum (covering green, digital, entrepreneurial and resilience skills for PM) complemented by innovative teaching methods (i.e. EIT Manufacturing's Teaching Factory Concept), micro-credential certification and bespoke digital

learning and co-creation platform for upskilling the current and future PM workforce and tackling skill gaps and mis-matches via skill forecasting and policy making.

- Helping PM companies and related service provider SMEs achieve corporate social responsibility by directly impacting on reducing environmental damage, diminishing social and societal risks and boosting their revenues.
- Stimulating a sense of initiative and entrepreneurial attitudes with regards to achieving resilient PM solutions, mind-sets and skills in adult, vocational and higher education learners.
- Facilitating the flow and co-creation of PM knowledge between higher education, VET actors, research, the public sector and the business sector in the field of PM in order to jointly contribute to upskilling and regional economic growth by developing capacities and clusters in the field of PM.
- Building and supporting effective and efficient PM higher education and vocational education and training systems delivered via a joint digital platform, which enables connectivity and inclusivity, contributing to innovation and equal access to high quality education for all in the emerging work field of PM.

B. Aim & objectives of the quality assurance methodology

The Quality Assurance Plan will describe in detail issues such as the following: 1) Actionable and effective guidance for achieving high-quality standards for all project's activities. 2) Detailed rules and procedures for online and offline dissemination actions in conformance with legal and ethical values. 3) Effective monitoring and control processes. 4) Models and templates for the project's deliverables and reports for easy and effective monitoring.

Each framework will establish the basic ground to be followed by all consortium members.

Objectives of the Quality Assurance

1. To ensure the project timescales and deliverables are realistic and are closely monitored and if necessary adjusted throughout the lifetime of the project
2. To monitor that the project runs to the proposed budget throughout the lifetime of the project
3. To monitor that the engagement with all project target groups is conducted to a high standard ensuring the necessary outcomes are achieved
4. To give advice and guidance to the project manager and the project team during the course of the project and encourage them to re-visit timescales, outcomes and outputs throughout the project
5. To produce an Exploitation and intellectual property agreement and strategy
6. To develop Quality standards for open innovation and co-creation framework

C. Overall quality assurance tasks

Quality assurance & evaluation: A quality plan will be developed to define specific quality performance indicators in each output of the project based on: (i) process and project management, (ii) partnership; (iii) results.

The quality plan will:

- define all the evaluation tools that will be used;
- describe clear evaluation criteria;
- create a shared understanding of the purposes, use, and users of the evaluation results;
- foster project's transparency to stakeholders and decision makers;
- facilitate evaluation capacity building among partners and stakeholders and also best evaluation practices.

The evaluation procedure will be based on:

- Analysis of project outputs and long-term outcomes (including the identification of improvements);
- Observations of interactions during implementation of all project activities;
- Surveys of personnel from partner organisations;
- Evaluation forms from participants in dissemination events and PreMETS blended pilots;
- Assessment of the skill-gap mitigation of target groups (beginning vs end of the project) via competence grids;
- External peer review based on an External Quality Assurance Board (EQAB). The EQAB members (scientists, industrial & policy representatives) are internationally renowned, independent experts working in the areas covered by PreMETS. The EQAB will review technical results of the project and give non-binding advice towards further advancements to be achieved. They will join PreMETS project meetings once per year;
- External evaluation with mid term and final reports by an appointed External Evaluator (see WP6).

Monitoring and evaluation process: PreMETS' quality processes will be led by HELIXCONNECT, specifically by Dr Adrian Solomon (quality assurance manager – QAM) who has strong expertise in producing high quality Erasmus+ project results. He will chair a quality assurance committee (QAC) composed of members from each partner organisation.

The Quality Assurance Manager (from HELIXCONNECT), Project Manager (from CERTH), the Steering Group, QAC & EQAB will have the task of ensuring monitoring and evaluation of the progress made towards objectives and results envisaged.

Quality control and evaluation points:

- Financial management:
 - formal reporting, every 6 months;
 - informal reporting - every 3 months;
- Project implementation (timeline) quality check during the monthly calls;
- Deliverable/result/activity sign off timeline, to be submitted to quality control 2 months prior to sign off deadline to be subjected to internal peer review and 1 month before sign-off to external peer review (to the external advisory board). This applies to both formal results as well as to progress results (i.e. pilot methodologies, dissemination materials, etc all broken down per task define in each WP);
- Staff engagement and involvement levels, to be monitored every 3 months via surveys;
- Project meeting evaluation: right after their accomplishment using an online questionnaire developed by HELIXCONNECT and focusing on 3 dimensions: before the meeting, during the meeting and after the meeting;
- Evaluation of dissemination events will be done using evaluation questionnaires (right after each event) developed by HELIXCONNECT focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitators, personal experience;
- Evaluation of the platform pilots will be done using evaluation questionnaires (before & after each event) developed by HELIXCONNECT focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitators, personal experience, interaction & engagement, ease of technology use, competence level (before and after);
- All the above will be integrated into Interim quality reports - every 6 months;
- External evaluation by an appointed evaluator (mid term and final).

All of the above quality checks will be built around SWOT analyses items: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats, both in a quantitative and qualitative assessment in order to enable a true improvement identification.

In order to successfully implement the vision of PreMETS QAP, the kaizen methodology will be adopted and the will imply: teamwork, personal discipline, improved morale and engagement, quality circles, and constant suggestions for improvement. On top of this, quality assurance is deeply embedded in each WP and activity development via internal and external peer-review stages (as it can be seen in the WP development tasks).

A timeline of the quality assurance actions consists of:

- **Month 1** - QAP will be developed containing specific key performance indicators (KPIs) and guidelines for the project implementation and WP development Quality assurance

monitoring spreadsheets also made available on the shared Google Drive File. A first meeting of the QAC will be organised.

- **Months 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24, 27, 30, 33** - trimestrial quality assurance monitoring meetings/check-ups (cross-checking the indicators and identifying potential risks/improvement opportunities) at the QAC and EQAB intervention level. The QAC and EQAB will hold online meetings to facilitate the effective quality assurance process.
- **Months 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36 (during the formal project meetings)**, QAC meetings will also take place to formally report on quality standards and formally deploy/co-create corrective measures.
- **Months 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36:** formal quality assurance monitoring reports will be issued by HELIXCONNECT.

Quality assurance monitoring will be done via a commonly shared spreadsheet. Every activity and sub-activity will have a sheet, which will be filled out by the responsible institution of the activity/sub-activity, providing information as start and end date, outcomes/outputs, indicators, or source of verification. Within each sheet, a link to at the folder containing the output/activity development will be provided. The organisation responsible for the activity will be asked to upload to this folder all the complementary documentation that supports the Outcomes/Outputs, especially those related to the Source of Verification. The indicators for measuring the quality and achievement of project activities consist of the following categories (HELIXCONNECT will develop the evaluation tools which will be peer-reviews by the QAC and EQAB):

PROJECT MEETINGS: all project meetings will be evaluated right after their implementation using an online questionnaire developed by HELIXCONNECT and focusing on 3 dimensions: before the meeting (preparations, agenda), during the meeting (effectiveness) and after the meeting (minutes, registers).

DISSEMINATION EVENTS: will be evaluated using evaluation questionnaires focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitation, personal experience.

VIRTUAL PILOTS: will be done using evaluation questionnaires focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitators, personal experience, interaction & engagement.

OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE (OER): Degree of alignment to standards, Quality of explanation of the subject matter, Utility of materials designed to support teaching - Quality of assessment, Quality of technological interactivity, Quality of instructional and practice exercises, Assurance of accessibility, Content quality, Motivation, Presentation design - Usability, Accessibility, Educational value, Overall rating.

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION: Timely implementation of tasks (minimum delay), Compliance with the rules of the funding program (no deviation), Continuous and transparent flow of information through the online depository (min. 90% of project documentation is shared through the Google drive).

SATISFACTION INDICATORS: positive feedback and satisfaction from the target groups with regards to the project outputs (85%), internal staff satisfaction from working on the project (85%).

The project quality assurance and evaluation activities (what, how, where) and division of work are presented in Annex 1 while the specific deliverables (outputs/outcomes) are presented in Annex 2.

D. Quality assurance indicators

The extent to which PreMETS's results and objectives have been met will be measured against the following broad categories of indicators:

- measures concerning impact on the target groups
- measures of behavioural change
- measures of quality of the outputs that have been developed
- measures of the dissemination and exploitation capacity

QUALITY RISK MITIGATION MECHANISMS:

- Clear definition of roles of the QAC
- Engagement with EQAB
- 3-month quality checks
- Concrete indicators in the QAP at various levels (prototype/concept, interim draft and final draft)

A sample of the quality assurance and evaluation indicators can be found in Annex 3.

E. Quality assurance methodological approach

Firstly, in their relationships within the overall consortium, each project partner shall be committed to the following rules and requirements.

Being responsive

To contribute to the value and effectiveness of the Project, it is vital that Project Partners respond to messages, enquiries and requests quickly and comprehensively. The following principles must be implemented:

- A reasonable time limit will be enforced for acknowledging receipt of messages: inquiries should be responded to within 5 working days,
- Project Partners will always provide a response, no matter what the outcome,
- Necessary tools must be in place to immediately inform other Project Partners of staff absence or office closure which will affect the above response time limits and Network Partners must always provide an alternative contact or expected date of return,
- Regularly check all incoming information and perform any required actions to the deadlines requested,

- Inform Consortium Coordinator of any issues which could affect the proper functioning of the consortium.

Dealing with non-responsive partners:

- In the first instance, the partner will be e-mailed by the project coordinator to enquire as to any concerns that may be preventing them from completing tasks. If no reply:
- Follow up e-mail will be sent with a specific to-do list and deadlines attached. At this time, this partner will be encouraged to call the project leader with specific times given. If no reply:
- Follow up email stressing the urgency of getting in touch and the implication of further delays for the project. The coordinator shall call the partner. If no reply:
- Registered official letter 1 to the Partner and its Legal representative offering an opportunity to negotiate deadlines to support the non-responsive partner. If no reply:
- Registered official letter 2 to Partner and its Legal representative setting a formal deadline for the partner to communicate problems/ complete work. If no reply:
- Registered official letter 3 to the Partner and its Legal representative dissolving its participation in the partnership.

Behave professionally at all times, be cooperative and try to find synergies

To qualitatively guarantee the excellence of the project, project partners are required to be dedicated to providing a professional service to their colleagues within the consortia. To uphold the professionalism of the consortium, partners must:

- Respect mutually established deadlines and be accountable for agreed measures and rules of the consortia,
- Follow agreed consortium processes and procedures at all times,
- Make the consortia aware of areas of expertise, through consortia tools or otherwise, and be prepared to use this expertise when assistance is requested from another partner,
- Be realistic in the level of support they can offer a colleague and communicate any difficulties that arise in delivering this support,
- Endeavour to continuously update and improve the skills of individual staff members to help enhance the knowledge and expertise of the consortia overall.

Share important information within the consortium

A two-way flow of important information between consortium coordinator and project partners is vital to ensure successful communication. For its part, consortium coordinator is responsible for:

- The dissemination of all correspondence with regards to project related activities,

- The provision of sufficient notice of deadlines for actions relating to reporting or contractual issues.

Contributing to the spirit of the project consortium

Sharing a common vision, aims and values will enhance the commitment, enthusiasm and effectiveness of the consortium, as well as allowing partners to learn from one another and share good practices.

To maintain this project spirit, project partners should:

- Be supportive and cooperative with their project colleagues while striving to make trusting, sustainable relationships,
- Treat other as they would expect to be treated themselves,
- Ensure contact details, changes in personnel and areas of expertise are kept up to date via consortium tools which will allow any partner to find the most appropriate contact quickly and confidently.

Secondly, To ensure good quality of the project's work processes, activities and products, especially all Work packages, activities and deliverables in the frame of the project the 'PDCA' cycle will be implemented as continuous improvement process. It consists of the following four steps: "Plan → Do → Check → Act (PDCA)".

Plan: The "plan" means to establish the way to complete the projects' objectives and achieve project results according to the expected predictions. The first plan will be provided by work package lead partners; each partner will follow this plan to plan its implementation within their own organisation.

Do: Subsequently the following "do" step ensures that new processes among partners, coordinator and third parties (like stakeholders, target group etc.) are encouraging an implementation under controlled circumstances. They shall be committed to implement the foreseen plan in time and with the foreseen results.

Check: The "checking" process commences when partners' or third parties' activities, implementation, communication and key project processes are evaluated – which, in this project will be an on-going process. The results will be evaluated according to a joint methodology in order to identify changes and initiate modifications where necessary.

Act: The final stage of the cycle introduces measures to standardise procedures within the projects' development or make improvement to enhance these. This will be managed by answering to and applying recommendations found upon the above described evaluation within the step 'check'.

Through this cycle, project partners and coordinator are provided with the opportunity to observe, assess and refine all the projects processes and outcomes.

The quality assurance process will focus on the work packages and deliverables and will be performed according to the following procedure:

Internal Quality Evaluation (peer review system)

The internal quality evaluation is mainly based on the questionnaires (see the appendix) that cover standardised questions about the realisation of the project.

It enables to find out how the project's goals and activities are carried out (identification, completion with respect to timelines), assess the progress of the project (evaluation of progress so far), identify project problems if any (with internal and/or external communication, deadlines, financial, technical, organisation, administrative) with the ways/suggestions to overcome them, Capture significant details about activities and outputs/results of communication / open innovation and co creation and dissemination throughout the project lifestyle (one of the questions is devoted to open innovation

and co-creation & dissemination activities). The internal quality evaluation will be made also during partners' meetings, online meetings, phone and e-mail contacts.

Evaluation questionnaires will contain questions enabling broader description and deeper assessment of different project deliverables/outputs as well as feedback/comments from stakeholders. The Bi-Yearly Monitoring/Evaluation Questionnaire Form will be completed by project partners' staff (managed by Helixconnect) .

The other evaluation questionnaires will be collected by all partners involved and sent to the partner responsible for specific deliverable to prepare cumulative assessment of the deliverable/IO.

The role of all Partners:

- giving information and data on the Project performance and Progress – feeding the Quality Assurance evaluation system,
- collecting info/feedback from stakeholders and end-users,
- contributing to and updating evaluations/reports,
- co-operating in early detection and solving of problems.

The role of HELIXCONNECT :

- leading quality assurance and activities within,
- co-ordinating Partners' input,
- preparing evaluations/reports.

All answers will be collected, analysed and use for evaluation reports.

F. Quality assurance best practices

Evaluation is a process which:

- (a) Supports a project, by measuring the extent to which the objectives are met,
- (b) Identifies achievements,
- (c) Identifies areas for improvement,
- (d) Encourages decisions to be taken, including changes to project objectives and/or methodologies.

Quality assurance is a component of quality management and it is focused on providing confidence that quality requirements will be fulfilled (ISO 9000).

Below it is given an overview of concepts and terms concerning quality assessment and evaluation based on best practices from the SUSTAIN-CE project (Erasmus+ KA2).

C O N C E P T S T E R M S	QUALITY	Quality can be determined by comparing a set of inherent characteristics with a set of requirements. If those inherent characteristics meet all requirements, high or excellent quality is achieved. If those characteristics do not meet all requirements, a low or poor level of quality is achieved. Note: Quality is always relative to a set of requirements.
	EVALUATION	Systematic collection and analysis of information on the actual performance of a project. Its aim is to analyse the relevance, progress, success and cost-effectiveness of the project. An evaluation compares planned results with the actual results of a project. It is a diagnostic tool.
	MONITORING	Continuing management exercise. Its aim is to supervise the accounting and administrative processes of a project. When implementing a project, monitoring deals almost exclusively with the conversion of inputs into outputs. This exercise will help to evaluate if what was supposed to be done really is. Adjustments to the project are possible when monitoring is done throughout the project management life cycle.
	PERFORMANCE MEASURES	Indicators that provide information (either quantitative or qualitative) on the extent to which the results of a project have been achieved. Evaluation is often confused with measures used to evaluate. Any activity which aims at interpreting results, or data obtained from measures, are part of an evaluation. To assure that the evaluation process leads to good decision-making, it must rest on correct and precise measures.
	EFFICIENCY	Refers to producing planned outputs within budgetary limits and established deadlines. For example: Was the implementation of the project well managed?
	EFFECTIVENESS	Refers to achieving planned results and contributing to attain established goals and objectives. For example: To what extent were the project's objectives achieved?
	IMPACT	Refers to the intended or unintended, negative or positive, consequences of a project, some of which happen only sometime after the end of the project. For example: What were the consequences and the effects of the project for the target groups?
	GOALS	A general statement of desired outcomes to be achieved over a specified period of time (the reasons for which the National Agency wishes to undertake the project).
	OBJECTIVES	The essential and long-term benefits towards which efforts are directed and for which outputs are to be produced.
	OUTPUTS	Tangible products (including services and events) that are necessary to achieve the objectives of the project and delivered to the project's target groups and stakeholders. Outputs relate to the completion (rather than the conduct) of activities and are the type of results over which partners have a high degree of influence. They are also the specific results obtained from the management of inputs.
	INPUTS	Activities and resources (human, material, financial) used to carry out activities, produce outputs and achieve results.
	RESULTS	The consequences or changes directly attributed to the activities of the project. The results achieved may be measured with respect to the inputs, outputs, goals and objectives of the project.
	PRODUCT QUALITY	The quality of a product is the degree to which it satisfies a specified set of attributes or requirements.
INDICATORS	A description of the project's objectives in terms of quantity, quality, target group(s), time and place.	

Section 2. Applied Quality Assurance Guide (T6.3)

Introduction

This guide aims to provide guidance to all partners involved in the PreMETS project on implementing high-quality standards and effectively communicating quality assurance related data. The report outlines the strategies and best practices to ensure that the project adheres to the defined quality standards and communicates progress to the Quality Assurance Manager. The Applied Quality Assurance guide is a practical guide that complements the broader Quality Assurance Plan created in Task 6.1. It provides clear instructions and actionable steps for the project team members to implement quality assurance measures within their respective areas. The success of the project greatly depends on maintaining a robust quality assurance process, and this guide will serve as a reference to achieve that goal.

Understanding your role

Clarity of Responsibilities

Understand your role and responsibilities within the project. Clearly identify the tasks and deliverables that fall under your area of responsibility. This clarity will help you define quality expectations.

Alignment with Project Goals

Ensure that your tasks and activities align with the broader project goals and objectives. This alignment will guide your efforts in implementing quality measures that contribute to the project's success.

Conduct Regular Quality Checks

Schedule regular quality checks and audits at critical milestones or phases of the research project. Utilize the QAP as a checklist to assess compliance with defined quality standards. Identify any deviations from the standards and record them for further action.

Implement Corrective and Preventive Actions

When encountering quality issues, prompt corrective actions will be undertaken to effectively tackle the underlying causes. All corrective actions will be meticulously documented within the project's issue tracking system, with designated responsibilities assigned for their resolution. In cases where an issue persists without resolution, escalation to the Quality Assurance Manager and the Project Coordinator will be pursued for further guidance.

Follow Quality Standards

Quality assurance, as defined by Helix in T6.1, is an integral part of quality management. Its primary objective is to instill confidence that the established quality requirements for the PreMETS project will be met effectively. In accordance with the ISO 9000 standard, which is a widely recognized framework for quality management, quality assurance encompasses systematic processes and practices that contribute to the consistent delivery of high-quality outcomes.

Familiarizing yourself with the core principles of quality assurance serves as a crucial foundation for ensuring the success of your work package or task. By understanding the essence of quality assurance, you equip yourself with the necessary knowledge to implement actions that not only meet project requirements but also uphold the project's reputation for excellence.

Implementing High-Quality Standards

- a. **Self-Assessment:** Begin by assessing your work package or task to identify the specific quality requirements and standards that apply. Understand how these standards align with the project's overall goals and objectives.
- b. **Alignment with Project Objectives:** Ensure that the quality standards you implement align with the project's objectives and the Quality Assurance Plan. This alignment guarantees that your contributions contribute positively to the project's success.

- c. Detailed Planning: Create a detailed plan outlining how you will meet the established quality standards. Define key milestones, activities, responsibilities, and timelines. This plan will serve as a roadmap for implementing quality measures effectively.

Establish Documentation and Record-Keeping Procedures

Record Keeping

Documenting your efforts provides a clear record of your commitment to quality. A standardized template will be developed to suit the project's requirements, and its utilization will be mandatory for all partners' reports. This template will promote consistency and the streamlining of the reporting process. Clear instructions on documentation procedures and individual responsibilities will be provided to all team members to ensure coherent practices. To enhance accessibility and organization, a Google Drive Folder has been created for project documents and records.

Communication Channels

Utilize established communication channels to report on your quality-related activities. Regularly update the Quality Assurance Manager on your progress, challenges, and successes. Partners are encouraged to participate in regularly scheduled meetings and discuss with the Quality Assurance Manager ongoing quality assurance efforts, progress, and challenges. Engage with the Quality Assurance Manager to seek guidance, share progress, and address any challenges you encounter. Collaboration ensures that you're aligned with project-wide quality objectives.

Training and Skill Development

Assess the team's skills and knowledge gaps related to their respective responsibilities. Organize internal training sessions (through your organization) or workshops to enhance technical expertise and understanding of quality standards. Encourage team members to pursue relevant certifications or courses to improve their capabilities.

Foster Collaboration and Feedback

Promote an open and collaborative environment where team members can freely discuss quality-related matters and provide feedback. Encourage cross-functional discussions to address interrelated quality issues. Regularly seek feedback from team members on the effectiveness of the quality assurance process.

Continuous Improvement

Reflect on your experiences and outcomes to identify lessons learned. What worked well? What can be improved? Learning from experiences contributes to refining your quality approach. Suggest necessary adjustments to the QAP based on feedback and evaluation. Apply the lessons learned to enhance your quality assurance practices. Implement changes iteratively to continuously improve the quality of your work.

External Evaluation and Improvement

The Role of External Evaluator

Understand the importance of the External Evaluator in assessing project progress and outcomes objectively. The External Evaluator provides an independent perspective to ensure transparency and quality.

Engaging with External Evaluator

Cooperate with the External Evaluator by providing the necessary information, data, and access to project materials. This collaboration facilitates a comprehensive evaluation of project performance.

Incorporating Feedback

Utilize feedback and recommendations from the External Evaluator to refine your quality assurance measures. Adapt your practices based on their insights to enhance overall project quality.

Conclusion

This guide equips you with practical steps to implement quality assurance measures within your area of responsibility. Your commitment to quality is essential for the success of the PreMETS project. By

following these instructions, you contribute to a culture of excellence, collaboration, and continuous improvement.

Annex 1. Work Package 6: Monitoring and evaluation activities (what, how, where) and division of work

Task No (continuous numbering linked to WP)	Task Name	Description	Participants		In-kind Contributions and Subcontracting (Yes/No and which)
			Name	Role (COO, BEN, AE, AP, OTHER)	
T6.1	Quality assurance plan	The Quality Assurance Plan will be a detailed and thorough document which will be drafted at the early stages of the project. The Quality Assurance Plan will describe in detail issues such as the following: 1) Actionable and effective guidance for achieving high-quality standards for all project's activities. 2) Detailed rules and procedures for online and offline dissemination actions in conformance with legal and ethical values. 3) Effective monitoring and control processes. 4) Models and templates for the project's deliverables and reports for easy and effective monitoring. Each framework will establish the basic ground to be followed by all consortium members.	HELIX	BEN	N/A
T6.2	VET and Higher Education hybrid learning quality assurance plan	This document will accompany the main Quality Assurance Plan and will be focusing on the activities directly related to the development of the hybrid PreMETS learning material and training delivery courses from the platform. Since PreMETS learning activities are a complex set of actions and materials, the Hybrid Quality Assurance Plan will flesh-out a comprehensive list of quality assurance standards for the training delivery methods, PreMETS learning content and the pedagogical dimensions of the training programme. ISIM will issue a guide for the context of VET education while MUB for higher education.	ISIM MUB	BEN BEN	N/A
T6.3	Applied quality assurance guide	During the project's kick-off meeting, work-package leaders and task collaborators will be effectively guided on the ways to put to practice high-quality standards developed within their area of responsibility and the communication means to offer quality-assurance related data to the Quality Assurance Manager. This initial and practical guidance step is important for enhancing the overall quality culture for a successful project implementation.	ATC	BEN	N/A
T6.4	Periodic quality reviews	During this task the Quality Assurance Plan will be implemented following the respective guides and rules. The Quality Assurance Manager (QAM) performs on-going monitoring of all work packages with a focus on implementation procedures. Upon the project's initiation, and the later creation of substantial outcomes, the QAM will materialise quality checks (every 6	CERTH YET UPI HELIX ISIM INTEL EITM MUB	COO BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	All listed partners will provide at least 20% in-kind contribution for the content development.

		months) to verify they meet the project’s initial objectives and characteristics. The QAM directly reports to the Steering Committee offering the results of 6 semestrial and 3 annual quality reviews to feed into the project progress reports and in the overall interim and final evaluation reports to EACEA. Quality review reports will be produced and describe the activities in detail after the project’s main intellectual outputs are produced. If deviations from high-quality standards are noticed, the QAM reports to the Steering Committee, and work with the EQAB to identify certain corrective actions.	LCC, DB ACC,WEG ATC	BEN BEN BEN	
T6.5	External evaluator selection	The project’s managerial boards will devise certain selection criteria for contracting the External Evaluator. The whole process will be designed to warrant quality, transparency and objectiveness of the external assessment. The Steering Committee should approve the selection procedure. The External Evaluator must be qualified on certain skills and qualifications, such as relevant assessment experience, lack of conflict of interest, etc. CERTH as the lead partner together with HELIX and ATC will prepare and carry out the tender for the External Evaluator. The call will be communicated in the project and partners’ websites and distributed across the academic and other research networks across Europe. The selection procedure will be based on a two-step approach: 1) Interested Evaluators will communicate their interest by submitting to CERTH their cv, references and motivation letter. The most qualified applicants will be shortlisted after an initial review of the applications. 2) The most promising candidates will be interviewed by CERTH and members of the Steering Committee.	CERTH YET UPI HELIX ISIM INTEL EITM MUB LCC DB ACC WEG ATC	COO BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	N/A
T6.6	External evaluation strategy	The selected external evaluator will create a comprehensive list of important results and outcomes from every work package and will determine their impact weight to the project. Relevant data sources will be identified, along with the timing of the evaluation reports and relevant timelines. Analytical tools for the evaluation process will also be identified, such as the project’s progress reports, deliverables, feedback from stakeholders, online questionnaires, interview guides, statistical methods, etc. All this material will be compiled into a workable Evaluation Blueprint document which will be distributed to all the project’s partners and after their feedback will be finalised.	External Evaluator CERTH YET,UPI,H ELIX ,ISIM INTEL EITM MUB,LCC DB,ACC WEG,ATC	OTHER COO BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	All listed partners will provide at least 20% in-kind contribution for the content development.
T6.7	External evaluation deployment	The External Evaluator will implement the assessment process based on identified impact factors (results and outcomes influencing impact) and prepare 2 interim and one final	External Evaluator CERTH YET, UPI	OTHER COO BEN BEN	All listed partners will provide at least 20% in-kind contribution for the

		evaluations to be integrated in interim and final reporting to EACEA. The reports will identify risk developments of project implementation and signal the Steering Committee, EQAB and the project's internal managerial committees for corrective actions if needed.	HELIX SIM, INTEL EITM,MU B,LCC DB, ACC WEG, ATC	BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	content development.
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Annex 2. The project quality assurance and evaluation specific deliverables (outputs/outcomes).

Deliverable No (continuous numbering linked to WP)	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month number)	Description (including format and language)
D6.1	Macro quality assurance plan	6	HELIX	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M3	An integrated report (80 pages) containing: Quality assurance plan (Task 6.1), VET/HEI quality assurance guidelines (Task 6.2) and the applied quality assurance guide (Task 6.3). Will be issued in EN, RO, GR, IT, DE, NE, SRB.
D6.2	Internal quality assurance report	6	HELIX	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M18 and M36	An integrated quality assurance report issued as a result of period quality controls of all the declared indicators. One interim report (50 pages) and one updated final report (50 pages) will be issued in English.
D6.3	External evaluation strategy	6	External Evaluator	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M6	An initial report explaining the external evaluation (at least 50 pages in English).
D6.4	External evaluation report	6	External Evaluator	[R — Document, report]	[PU — Public]	M18 and M36	One interim report (50 pages) and one updated final report (50 pages) will be issued in English as part of the external evaluation task.

Annex 3. Quality assurance and evaluation indicators during the project implementation timeline

Indicator	Base value	Target value	Measurement unit	Measurement method
PM modules developed and integrated into university curricula (quant)	0	6	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
PM modules developed and integrated into VET curricula (quant)	0	6	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
Number of train-the-trainers modules (quant)	0	8	Number of modules	Complete learning pack
Number of trained learners on PM (quant)	0	1000	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of trained trainers in PM (quant)	0	250	# of certifications	Record/log keeping
Number of certified learners via microcredentials (quant)	0	500	# of certifications	Record/log keeping
Number of learners from social groups at risk involved in the project (quant)	0	300	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of learners involved in blended work based learning secondments (quant)	0	50	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of companies engaged in the PreMETS platform (quant)	0	20	Number of companies	Record/log keeping
Number of universities and VET centres that will uptake the PreMETS platform (quant)	0	50	Number of institutions	Record/log keeping
Number of modernised university and VET related PM curricula (quant)	0	25	Number of units	Record/log keeping
Learner satisfaction with regards to the PreMETS online platform (quant + qual) - 35% increase from day 1 to end of training	0	> 85% satisfaction with	1-5 scale index	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction
Make PM workforce more productive (quant)	Index-based	20% increase	Productivity metrics	Checking company reports
Learner digital competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	20% increase	1-5 point scale for DigComp	Self-assessed DigComp survey (pre and post training)

Learner green competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	15% increase	1-5 point scale for GreenComp	Self-assessed GreenComp survey (pre and post training)
Learner entrepreneurship competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	25% increase	1-5 point scale for EntreComp	Self-assessed EntreComp survey (pre and post training)
Trainer competence increase with regards to online education delivery (sample of 250 trainers) (quant)	after pre-assessment	25% increase	1-5 point scale for DigCompEdu	Self-assessed DigCompEdu survey (pre and post training)
Number of dropouts from university/VET (quant)	after pre-assessment	15% decrease	Number of learners	Comparing dropouts in year 1 and in year 3 learners database
Amount of funding obtained to sustain PreMETS activities (quant)	0	500 000 EUR	EUR	Combined budget from new projects acquired to sustain PreMETS' efforts
# of policy makers interested to use PreMETS platform for promoting regional safety, sustainability and industrial resilience (quant)	0	10	Number of policy makers	Record/log keeping
Number of companies outside of the consortium interested to use PreMETS platform for upskilling their employees (quant)	0	30	Number of companies	Record/log keeping
Make online education more inclusive (quant + qual)	after pre-assessment	45% increase	Subjective/personal reflections	Pre and post assessment (before and after the trainings)
Degree of learners feeling empowered to be in charge of their own learning path (quant + qual)	TBD after pre-assessment	30% increase	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Pre and post assessment (before and after the trainings)
Increase of employability	Statistical average	15-30% increase in 6-12 months	Percentage	Comparing yearly statistics
Overall satisfaction level of the involved project team (quant + qual)	0	>85%	Subjective reflections	Post assessment at the project completion

Social media engagements / reactions (quant)	0	100 000	# of reaction	Social media metrics
Website visitors (quant)	0	5000	# of visitors	Google analytics
Implementation conformance (quant)	0	<10% change	Percentage	Measuring timeline changes